

Clinicohaematological and Biochemical Profile of Anemia in Pediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia is a considerable public health issue affecting children globally, particularly in developing countries. It leads to impaired cognitive and physical development, increased infection risk, and poor quality of life. Nutritional deficiencies, particularly iron deficiency, are the primary causes of pediatric anemia. This study aims to evaluate the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles of anemia in the pediatric population at BMIMS Pawapuri, and to analyze the relationship between anemia, nutritional status, and socioeconomic factors.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was carried out, involving 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia. Data were collected on demographic details, clinical history, physical examination, and laboratory investigations, including complete blood count (CBC), serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), and serum ferritin. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0.

Results: The study included 100 children, with a mean hemoglobin level of 8.5 ± 1.2 g/dL. The majority (70%) had moderate anemia, while 20% had mild anemia and 10% severe anemia. Underweight children exhibited significantly lower serum iron (45 ± 12 µg/dL) and ferritin levels (15 ± 8 ng/mL) compared to children with normal weight (55 ± 15 µg/dL and 25 ± 10 ng/mL, respectively). A significant positive correlation was found between hemoglobin and serum ferritin ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.001$), and a negative correlation between hemoglobin and TIBC ($r = -0.55$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the critical role of nutritional status in pediatric anemia, with underweight children exhibiting more pronounced iron deficiency. Iron deficiency is a major contributor to anemia in this cohort, emphasizing the need for targeted nutritional interventions.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on evaluating specific dietary and supplementation strategies to address iron deficiency. Public health policies should prioritize nutritional interventions and fortification programs to improve hematological outcomes in anemic children.

Keywords: Pediatric anemia, Iron deficiency, Nutritional status, Hematological profile, Serum ferritin.

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Introduction

Anaemia is a worldwide public health issue that has a substantial influence on children's morbidity and death, particularly in developing nations. The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that 42% of children under five suffer from anaemia globally [1]. The disease is typified by a decrease in haemoglobin concentration or red blood cell count, which results in inadequate oxygen delivery to tissues. Adverse developmental outcomes, such as stunted cognitive and physical development, heightened susceptibility to infections, and an all-around low quality of life, can arise from paediatric anaemia.

Children's anaemia has a complex aetiology, but the most common cause is a dietary insufficiency, namely an iron deficiency. Worldwide, almost half of all instances of anaemia in children are caused by iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) [2]. Hemoglobinopathies, infections, chronic illnesses, and deficits in vitamin B12 and folate are among additional causes. The incidence of anaemia in paediatric populations is further increased by dietary practices, socioeconomic variables, and recurrent illnesses.

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the complex interplay between nutritional status

and anemia. Undernutrition, characterized by insufficient intake of calories and essential nutrients, is a significant risk factor for anemia. Malnourished children are more likely to develop anemia due to inadequate dietary intake of iron and other micronutrients necessary for erythropoiesis [3]. Conversely, overweight and obesity in children are also emerging as contributors to anemia, with evidence suggesting that excess adiposity may impair iron metabolism and utilization.

Addressing pediatric anemia requires a multifaceted approach, encompassing dietary interventions, fortification programs, and public health strategies to reduce infection burden. Iron supplementation and food fortification have been widely implemented with varying degrees of success. However, the persistence of anemia highlights the need for tailored interventions that consider the underlying causes and context-specific factors affecting different populations [4].

Recent studies underscore the importance of continuous monitoring and updating intervention programs to reflect current trends and challenges in managing pediatric anemia [5]. This research contributes to the growing body of literature by offering updated data and analysis from a specific regional context, thus enhancing the overall understanding of pediatric anemia and informing future public health initiatives.

This study aimed at evaluating the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profile of anemia in the pediatric population.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place at BMIMS Pawapuri, India, spanning from May 2022 to May 2023.

Participants: A total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 1 to 18 years
- Diagnosed with anemia based on hemoglobin levels (Hb < 11 g/dL for children under 5 years, Hb < 12 g/dL for children aged 5-12 years, and Hb < 13 g/dL for adolescents)
- Patients whose guardians provided informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with chronic diseases
- Patients receiving blood transfusions within the last three months

- Patients with genetic disorders affecting hematological parameters

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by including a consecutive sample of eligible patients. Data collection was standardized to reduce information bias, and all laboratory tests were conducted in the same laboratory to avoid measurement bias.

Variables: Variables included age, gender, nutritional status, socioeconomic status, hemoglobin levels, hematocrit, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), serum ferritin, and other relevant biochemical markers.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured proforma which included:

- Demographic details: age, gender, and socioeconomic status
- Clinical history: symptoms, dietary history, and family history of anemia
- Physical examination: signs of pallor, jaundice, and other relevant findings
- Laboratory investigations: complete blood count (CBC), serum iron, TIBC, serum ferritin, and other relevant biochemical tests

Procedure

1. After obtaining informed consent from guardians, detailed clinical histories were recorded.
2. Physical examinations were performed, focusing on signs related to anemia.
3. Blood samples were collected for laboratory investigations.
4. Laboratory tests, including CBC, serum iron, TIBC, and serum ferritin, were conducted in the hospital's laboratory.
5. Data were recorded and analyzed to determine the clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles of the participants.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 25.0 was used to analyse the data. Whereas categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages, continuous variables were shown as means and standard deviations. For comparing categorical variables, chi-square tests were employed; for comparing continuous variables, t-tests or ANOVA were utilised. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written

informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

Table 1 provides a summary of the clinical and demographic features of the 100 paediatric anaemia patients that were included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Attributes

Characteristic	Percentage (%)
Age Group	
1-5 years	30.0
6-12 years	40.0
13-18 years	30.0
Gender	
Male	55.0
Females	45.0
Nutritional Status	
Normal	50.0
Underweight	35.0
Overweight	15.0
Socioeconomic Status	
Low	60.0
Middle	30.0
High	10.0

The mean hemoglobin level was found to be 8.5 ± 1.2 g/dL. The majority of the children (70%) had moderate anemia, while 20% had mild anemia, and 10% had severe anemia. Table 2 presents the distribution of hematological parameters.

Table 2: Hematological Parameters

Parameter	Mean \pm SD
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	8.5 ± 1.2
Hematocrit (%)	28 ± 3.5
MCV (fL)	75 ± 8
MCH (pg)	24 ± 3
Serum Iron (μ g/dL)	50 ± 15
TIBC (μ g/dL)	350 ± 45
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	20 ± 10

The mean serum iron levels were significantly lower in underweight children compared to those with normal weight (45 ± 12 μ g/dL vs. 55 ± 15 μ g/dL, $p = 0.02$). The TIBC was higher in underweight children (370 ± 40 μ g/dL) compared to those with normal weight (340 ± 50 μ g/dL), but

this variation was not statistically substantial ($p = 0.08$). Serum ferritin levels were significantly lower in the underweight group (15 ± 8 ng/mL) compared to the normal weight group (25 ± 10 ng/mL, $p = 0.01$).

Table 3: Biochemical Parameters by Nutritional Status

Parameter	Normal Weight	Underweight	p-value
Serum Iron (μ g/dL)	55 ± 15	45 ± 12	0.02
TIBC (μ g/dL)	340 ± 50	370 ± 40	0.08
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	25 ± 10	15 ± 8	0.01

Haemoglobin levels and serum ferritin were found to significantly positively correlate ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.001$). Haemoglobin levels and TIBC showed a significant negative connection ($r = -0.55$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Hemoglobin & Serum Iron	0.45	0.03
Hemoglobin & TIBC	-0.5	<0.01
Hemoglobin & Ferritin	0.65	<0.001

Discussion

The study included 100 pediatric patients with anemia, revealing significant insights into the

clinical, hematological, and biochemical profiles of the condition within this population. The age distribution was fairly balanced, with children aged

6-12 years comprising the largest group (40%), followed by those aged 1-5 years (30%) and 13-18 years (30%). The gender distribution showed a slight predominance of males (55%) over females (45%). Nutritional status varied, with half of the children having normal weight, 35% being underweight, and 15% being overweight. Most participants came from low socioeconomic backgrounds (60%).

Hematological analysis demonstrated that the mean hemoglobin level was 8.5 ± 1.2 g/dL, indicating that the majority of children (70%) had moderate anemia, with 20% having mild anemia and 10% severe anemia. The hematocrit, MCV, and MCH values were consistent with the anemic state of the patients. Biochemical profiles revealed mean serum iron levels of 50 ± 15 μ g/dL, TIBC of 350 ± 45 μ g/dL, and serum ferritin levels of 20 ± 10 ng/mL.

A detailed examination of biochemical parameters by nutritional status showed that underweight children had significantly lower serum iron (45 ± 12 μ g/dL) and ferritin levels (15 ± 8 ng/mL) compared to children with normal weight (55 ± 15 μ g/dL and 25 ± 10 ng/mL, respectively). These differences, with p-values of 0.02 and 0.01 respectively, were statistically significant. While underweight children had greater TIBC, the variation was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$).

Haemoglobin levels and serum ferritin showed a substantial positive association ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.001$), according to correlation analysis, suggesting that greater ferritin levels are related to higher haemoglobin levels. Furthermore, a noteworthy inverse relationship was found between TIBC and haemoglobin levels ($r = -0.55$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a drop in haemoglobin levels with an increase in TIBC.

The results underscore the critical role of nutritional status in the biochemical profile of anemic children, with underweight children exhibiting more pronounced iron deficiency. These findings suggest that iron deficiency is a major contributor to anemia in this population, highlighting the need for targeted nutritional interventions. Addressing iron deficiency through dietary improvements and supplementation could significantly improve hematological outcomes for anemic children.

Anemia in the pediatric population is a critical health concern with multifactorial etiologies, impacting growth, development, and overall health. A study on the clinicohematological profile of anemia in children was carried out. They found that the most common type of anemia was microcytic hypochromic anemia (47.73%), with iron deficiency being the leading cause (35.79%). Weakness, easy fatigability, and irritability were common symptoms, while pallor was a universal

sign [6]. A study provided an overview of potential etiologies and clinical and laboratory features of pediatric anemia. They emphasized the importance of identifying anemia early to prevent complications such as impaired growth and neurocognitive development [7].

A study assessed anemia among laborers and found a 29% prevalence rate. The study highlighted a higher prevalence among rural residents and lower socioeconomic classes, with significant occurrences in children under 5 years [8]. Anemia in children aged 0 to 18 years was studied. Iron deficiency anemia was the most common, particularly in the 1-6 years age group. Vitamin B12 and folic acid deficiencies were also significant causes, especially in older children [9].

A study examined anemia in infants and children. They found that microcytic hypochromic anemia and iron deficiency anemia were the most common types, with acute gastroenteritis being a frequent presenting condition [10]. A study on severe anemia in children was conducted at a tertiary care hospital. Nutritional anemia, particularly iron deficiency, was the most common cause. Malnutrition and infection were prevalent among these children [11].

Conclusion

The results indicate that anemia in the pediatric population is predominantly of moderate severity. Nutritional status significantly impacts biochemical parameters, with underweight children exhibiting lower serum iron and ferritin levels. The strong positive correlation between hemoglobin and serum ferritin suggests that iron deficiency is a major contributor to anemia in this cohort. These findings underscore the importance of nutritional interventions in the management of pediatric anemia. Future studies should explore the effectiveness of specific dietary and supplementation strategies to address iron deficiency and improve hematological outcomes in this population.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Future research should focus on evaluating specific dietary and supplementation strategies to address iron deficiency. Public health policies should prioritize nutritional interventions and fortification programs to improve hematological outcomes in anemic children.

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List of abbreviations:

CBC - Complete Blood Count

TIBC - Total Iron-Binding Capacity

IDA - Iron Deficiency Anemia

WHO - World Health Organization

Hb - Hemoglobin

SD - Standard Deviation

MCV - Mean Corpuscular Volume

MCH - Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin

SPSS - Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

ANOVA - Analysis of Variance

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References

1. World Health Organization. Anaemia. [Internet]. 2021. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/anaemia>
2. Kassebaum NJ, Jasrasaria R, Naghavi M, Wulf SK, Johns N, Lozano R, et al. A systematic analysis of global anemia burden from 1990 to 2010. *Blood*. 2018;123(5):615-24.
3. Global Burden of Disease Pediatrics Collaboration. Global and regional burden of childhood anemia in 2016. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*. 2020;4(3).
4. Pasricha SR, Tye-Din J, Muckenthaler MU, Swinkels DW. Iron deficiency. *The Lancet*. 2021;397(10270):233-48.
5. Thurnham DI. Nutrition and anemia in low-income countries. *Nutrition Reviews*. 2020;78(10):797-814.
6. Upadhyay P, Kanetkar S. Clinicohematological profile of anemia in pediatric (newborn to eighteen years) age group. *Int J Health Sci Res*. 2022.
7. McDaniel J, Sorge C. Diagnostic approach to anemia in childhood and adolescents. In: *Anemia in the Young and Old*. 2018.
8. Upreti R. Assessment of prevalence and profile of anemia among laborer of a known population. *Int J Adv Res Med*. 2019.
9. Marken P, Bharat V, Chawla S. Clinicohaematological and biochemical profile of anemia in pediatric age group. *Int J Res*. 2020; 7:552-556.
10. Nilofer F, Lilly RVM. Clinicohematological study of different patterns of anemia in infancy and childhood. *J Pharm Res*. 2021;33(20A):44-55.
11. Janjale A, Pande S, Sonawane R, Ahire NR, Sonawane S. A study of severe anemia in children in a tertiary care institute. *MVP J Med Sci*. 2018;5(1).